

FELLOWSHIP

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Hubballi City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories, concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot –built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance and cultural context of their cities.. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and develop thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is a emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Hubballi

Where are you from? Hubli.
Oh like from the Hooghly?
No, not that one, it's Hubli.
Oh!

Located in the Northern part of Karnataka, Hubli is my hometown. As a child, I took a one hour long to school. It was a long ride to the northwestern part of Hubli. I took this ride for 17 years and saw my city break, change, transform, evolve to the bits of it. From the lush green roads to a decade of never ending demolition and construction, I saw it all. Since 2012, my everyday ferry to school has felt like I'm living a Clayton Leigh's story, from Black Museum (Black Mirror S4, E6), where Clayton was stuck in an endless loop of reliving his painful moments of life. I am not the only Clayton, and this document is an attempt to unfold citizen's experiences on what it is to live in Hubli, what is happening and how they want the city to become in the coming years.

Everyday Life

What is it like to live in Hubli?

Jyoti, 51, a resident living in Hubli, narrates her daily routine. She lives in Shreya estate and travels everyday to the yoga academy at dollars colony where she teaches yoga. She finishes her work and heads back home on her private vehicle. When I ask her about how she spent her leisure time, she narrates on going on walks near the airport road. “This KLE road, it’s easy, peaceful. Take two rounds and do light yoga and come back”. She emphasizes on the empty roads, where it feels peaceful, she says it feels like away from the daily chaos. She walks there for 6 kms. While we were talking about how walking was important to her, she took me to her childhood days in the 1980's, where walking was not only a need but also an enjoyable activity. She walked everyday from her school, tuition and back home. Every Thursday, she walked to Sai Baba temple at chennamma circle. I ask her if she still visits the temple. She replied saying, going there for a walk now is a far fetched dream. She says:“ Back then there was a divine peacefulness, that you won’t feel now if i go there. Baba is the same. It feels very commercial now’. The peacefulness in the city has long exited the chat, as Chennemma circle has become the biggest traffic bottleneck in the city. The sense of commercialisation from the construction of roads, flyovers and even a mall in front of the temple. As a result, today Jyoti has “stopped going to the market for 3 years now. Because there are so many vehicles, almost touching each other”.

Another resident, Geeta who is currently a teacher, teaches at her school in the morning, comes back home and takes tuitions at home. She lives in bhairidevar koppa. She starts her day by taking the KSRTC bus from the bus stand that is right across her house. She gets off at an old bus stand, near chennamma circle to hop on another ride to reach school. That is her daily routine. On her day off, she usually visits her relatives or goes to Durgad bail market. But currently her pattern has changed due to ongoing construction in front of her house. Instead of just crossing the road to reach the bus stop, she takes the long route, this increases her travel time and the construction in front of her home and on the bus stand experiences a daily challenge of dust pollution.

What is it like to live in Hubli?

Nidhi, a 24 year old working professional, unfolds her daily routine. She says she works from home most of the time and on the occasions when she is bored, “you know, just go on a drive, Go to a cafe, if possible. Or like walking and eating and also shopping”.

She says that some days she really has nothing to do in the city. So she finds herself wandering through the clothing stores that are very accessible at “zudio, yousta, style union, all lined next to each other”. She says “sometimes, you also end up taking, like, a pooja chakkar, like, you know,. Like, a mall, you come, like, an entire circle”. This wasn’t the case for her in childhood.

She recalls, in childhood she had a lot of activities to engage herself in during leisure hours. “I lived in a close knit galli where I played everyday or did some activities”. This feeling passed when Nidhi shifted to an apartment and time changed. In her leisure time, she says “in Hubli you can’t hangout without friends”.

There is a lack of community initiatives and public spaces for her to hangout.

“I lived in a close knit galli where I played everyday or did some activities”. This feeling passed when I shifted to an apartment and time changed. In my leisure time, she says “in Hubli you can’t hangout without friends”.

Nidhi, 24

What is it like to live in Hubli?

Madhusudan, a working professional and a parent, describes his routine of going for a morning jog at BVB campus, post which he travels from Shirur park to shreya nagar on his private vehicle. He states he is mostly busy on his weekdays. However on weekends, he said “These days, I prefer traveling back to village life on weekends – places like Gadag or Sirsi. There are so many beautiful sites nearby, and it’s a nice break from the city”. He mentions the need to escape the city life, as hubli has grown and developed, attracting more people and traffic.

Secondly, Hubli is located close to popular tourist spots in Karnataka. But did he always spend his leisure time away from the city? When I asked him this question, he stated that during old times, he used to visit CBT market every sunday, go do some shopping and from there hop to “*moorusavir mutt* to have the famous idly”.

That summed his weekend. Although he still visits there, he likes to spend his time outside the city more often. This highlights his growing need to find a balance between growing speed city life and quieter village environments.

For college students, this case is very different. When I asked Haripriya about her daily routine when she lived in Hubli. She narrates her college days. Very plain and simple, she says her college time revolved around “going to college, coming back home, going to gym with Aishwarya, and then hanging out with her friends at the chai shai, which was right below the gym”.

She narrates on her monotonous schedule revolving around bunking college and going to gym and hanging out in the cafe.

Places of Belonging

In the past, Hubli's compact urban layout shaped its daily activities. Walking was not just a necessity but a way of life. "Everything was walkable from kale galli, Durgad Bail" Jyoti, 51, explains. "The bus stand, the market, the repair shops one round of walking, and all work would be done".

Local street vendors, cobblers, and repairmen thrived as residents navigated their errands with ease. Durgad Bail, for instance, was a hub of street food, where a few rupees spent on chaats brought immeasurable happiness.

However, as the city expanded with growing businesses and a rising population, the increase in vehicles and sprawling roads brought unprecedented traffic. The once-walkable charm of Hubli has faded, not just due to distance but also because walking is no longer as safe as it once was. Taking a vehicle is the norm to travel around the city, but when you do that, there is a bigger problem of parking. Jyoti complains the same: "Now vehicles have come, it's become a headache. You need to go and find parking".

Theaters that once dotted Coen Road, where students sneaked in for afternoon shows, have been replaced by malls.

For Jyoti, the heart of her childhood memories lies in her oni, Kale Oni, where houses stood close together in the bustling market area. "Enu irtiddilla andru ondh maja, heng time hog titt gott aag tiddila" [There was nothing in our galli, but still, there was some different fun. Never knew how time flied there]. Further into our conversation, she told me about the joy of living in her galli where she enjoyed living in a hustle bustle area, watching people pass by, celebrating the festivals like ganesh chaturthi, talk to her neighbours, and watching her kids play in front of houses. But now she expresses that the current state of place is completely different, having moved to an apartment in Gokul Road's Dollars Colon, one of Hubli's most upscale areas.

Jyoti reflects on the stark contrast between her past and present living environments. Transitioning from a close-knit community space to an apartment setting has brought an unexpected shift.

"Everything was walkable from kale galli (and) Durgad Bali- the bus stand, the market, the repair shops one round of walking, and all work would be done... Now vehicles have come, it's become a headache. You need to go and find parking".

- Jyoti, 51

"You didn't need to dress up to step outside. Now, in an apartment, you feel like you have to dress properly before going out," she explains. In the oni, stepping outside meant instantly seeing familiar faces, exchanging greetings, and engaging in spontaneous conversations. The streets themselves felt like an extension of home.

"Now we live in these apartments, right? There's no one around to talk to. It's just 'hello, hi' that's it. 'Had breakfast? Had lunch?' and nothing more," she adds.

For those who once lived in gallis, this shift is deeply felt. The warmth of community life, where interactions were effortless and bonds grew naturally, has been replaced by a more structured, distant way of living. What about the Galli I ask, and she says, "Slowly people are moving out and it is more commercial; only a few houses are left now..Earlier it used to be just residential". Kale Galli, today is located in Durgad Bail, which is the centre of Business and trade in Hubli. With growing business in the city, there is an immense demand for a market property.

 "Slowly people are moving out and it is more commercial; only a few houses are left now..Earlier it used to be just residential".
-A local resident

Subsequently, people have vacated their house and rented or sold it for commercial purposes.

Hubli's one of the most popular public spaces is Unkal Kare, which has been around for centuries. Most of the interviewees when asked about the place mentioned about spending their childhood leisure time here with their friends and family. One of the respondents, Suhasni, joyfully narrates her childhood memories spent at unkal lake.

Every summer, when her cousins from different city arrived at her place, they all would go to unkal lake. She says it's not just about going, but its a day-long event. An event which would start in the morning, where everyone gathered and made lunch together. They would pack lunch and collectively travel to unkal lake and spend their afternoon, enjoying their picnic spread. By the time lunch and games would get over it would be evening. She says "watching the sunset from there was the best part".

I ask her if this is the case even now? She says, currently, the lake is beautified but not allowed to have picnics. Subsequently, she says "Right now the whole idea is if anybody comes in we take them to the best restaurant in hubli. We finish food, next come back and then go for chai or something". It's not just Suhasini but also similar experiences with many other respondents.

 "Right now the whole idea is if anybody comes in we take them to the best restaurant in hubli. We finish food, next come back and then go for chai or something".
-Suhasin, Local Resident

Unkal lake has been a core memory in their childhood, but currently many don't go there. Another popular public space in Hubli is Nrupatunga betta. Jyoti in her earlier days, recalls " I used to go to Nruputunga betta every day for a morning walk, people warned me it's an isolated place, but i still went for the peace it offered". Jyoti holds special regards to this place as it was always quiet, calm, with no residential or commercial movements. Currently she has decided to abandon Betta and walk on the other side of the city. This change according to Jyoti is because "Betta is now residential".

Being a residential place means converting the farms there into plots, plots into buildings and walking around areas where there is rampant construction is not the best place source of peace.

Back in the time, it was not just the public space that provided the space for community engagement, but also the open roads and long routes to college and school. For Sumitra, back in the earlier days in 1990's she recalls her journey to college. She used to walk her way to college, with her friends from the old bus stand to PC Jabin college which is nearly 5 kilometers. The sense of walking brought her close to nature and it gave her a sense of happiness as everyone walked in groups, talked throughout the way. It was a group activity. However as the years evolved, she's seen massive changes on the same road. Currently working as a teacher right next to PC Jabin, she says "I have never in my life stopped three times to cross the road". With the development of BRTS lanes and smart city projects there are traffic signals implemented, it was never a thing in the city.

I entered the market to converse with the owner of the oldest hotel in Hubli. Mr Prashant, who is currently 70. I asked him about the place in Hubli where he felt belonged, and he recalled his childhood memories. Prashant joined early in business, but whenever he stole some time he spent it in the open railway grounds near keshwapur. Railway grounds was one of the oldest and largest grounds in the city. He said "I used to play games like gilli danda, marble balls, we played them alot". But immediately, he snaps into narrating about the changes that have happened there. He said that "Earlier anyone used to go, now there are tickets, restrictions on entry, with timings and security." Earlier there used to be two open grounds, the railway and the other Nehru ground. Unfortunately the city is left with only one open ground at Nehru Stadium which is open to everyone and is not ticketed.

Figure 1: Women sitting on Katti
Source: Author

Voices of Concern

Dust Pollution

“I fail to understand is yaha pe itna dust kyu hai. Yeh registan bhi nahi hai rajasthan bhi nahi hai. You see the sides of the roads. Yeh itna dust kyu hai”, asks Sanjay, a new resident of Hubli. When you take a walk on the main streets of Hubli, as Sanjay said, you will see soil on the road, subsequently dust particles in the air and slowly into your body. This has been a concerning problem for the citizens of Hubli since a decade, who share their day to day struggles, impact on their health, safety and living experiences.

Their concerns point towards impact on safety and health due to dust pollution in the Hubli. According to the CPCB Annual Report 2019-20, “the annual average of PM10 in Hubli was $75\mu\text{g}/\text{M}^3$ at Gokul Road”, which is far above the WHO standards, $20\mu\text{g}/\text{M}^3$. When the city’s state is way beyond the recognised limits, citizens’ health has and is subsequently bearing the brunt of this problem.

I asked xxx, 45, a school teacher who lives in Vidyanagar about dust pollution in the city and she responded saying that “I have developed a dust allergy, and it has worsened over time due to the dust in the city. Even my clothes feel dusty”. Citizen’s health in Hubli is being affected on a daily basis. This is not an isolated experience, it gravitates towards the same problem experienced by many others. Another resident, who is an architect, complains “I never had allergies before, now, I sneeze every time I pass through certain areas [like Old Bus stand]”. It’s not just these two, but every other participant who has voiced against the problem of persistent dust pollution in the city.

I enquired more with the local naturopathy doctor, to understand the implications and gravity of the problem. He disclosed that he receives “15-20 patients [weekly] with dust-related issues.”.

I ask him, is the problem just limited to dust allergy? He smiles and explains the science on how dust reacts with a human body, especially the PM 10 particles. He explains that inhaling oxygen, which has high contaminants of dust, puts pressure on the human lungs, which leads to increased cases of cough, cold. However, he warns citizens to be careful and cautious.

What starts with dust induced cough and cold can lead to long term damages, if not treated on time. He recalls a patient’s case, where the patient travelled on bike everyday to reach his factory. The patient developed cough and left it untreated for a while. This eventually led them to develop mild asthma.

Currently they are receiving treatment at their facility. Doctor xxx, warns that if problems persist without treatment it could lead to chronic asthma, TB, breathlessness, insomnia and even BP. His insights uncovered the gravity of the problem, where dust related health issues which are usually complained on daily basis, are ignored as inconvenience, could lead to chronic health issues if not treated on time.

Figure 2: A meme on the state of roads in Hubli.

Source: India Times

Dust Pollution

Isn't it just dust? Silently sitting on the leaves of otherwise green bushes, on the corners of the road, silently making its way to your house. It's not just silently impacting resident's health but also posing disruptive safety concerns. xxx, a Yoga instructor, 55, shares her distressing experience just a couple of months ago in 2024, where she fell twice on her way to work and got her ankle sprained on the second time. She recalls "It's a road problem, there are potholes every few meters, vehicles running at a dangerous speed and dust!".

Another resident, 31, share's their experience of living amidst the dusty roads dated sometime in 2016. She shares the story of her accident on the roads of shirur park, currently a well developed road. She recalls the day when "I was giving a ride to my helper and we fell due to an unseen pothole hidden by the dust". Such incidents are not random events, they are but consequences of far larger problems related to the state of Roads.

Potholes as the face of hubli and topic for conversation is a hint at the intensity of the problem. The problem being frequent road digging, and delayed implementation. Enquiring on this situation on the Northern side of Hubli, XXX, journalist describes the state of roads in front of her house in Madhura Colony.

Figure 3: Digging on a newly built road at Gokul Road
Source: Author

Figure 4: Digging to install the broken chamber pipes at Shirur Park
Source: Author

Transportation Challenges

She marks it as a “nice road” but they dug up for some reason/repair and it still hasn't progressed, subsequently “dust runs a lot more than it used to before”. When enquired about the situation of roads on the other end of the city in Gokul road, located in East, Jyoti complains that it's been more than 3 months, road digging is happening on all 4 sides of her apartment. She says “The work is slow, if at one side they have dug something it doesn't get over”. Delayed construction exposes the top soil for a period of time, this in combination with increased vehicular movement on such roads serves as a perfect recipe for dust pollution in Hubli. It is not just the digging, but also when the new roads are being made, are they of better quality?

Digging, poor condition of roads were a sufficient reason to stir up the dust in Hubli. But what made it worse, like a cherry on this mess was prolonged or rather delayed construction of infrastructure projects. Haripriya, 25, presents her observation: “There's a massive slowdown of infrastructure projects. Like, when I came six months ago or when I came three months ago, the situation still looks pretty much the same. So that's, I think, adding up to the dust pollution”. For citizens this is a growing concern, as they see no improvement and on top of that face the brunt of it on a day to day basis. Residents who pass roads on a daily basis, have witnessed the infrastructural changes, its impact on their daily lives on a micro level. XXX's narrates his instance of travelling through Hubli's prominent circle, called Chennamma circle which is located at the heart of the city. He states his observation that there was no dust pollution before few years ago, he associates this problem with road development and hints at the cause: “I've been seeing this [Old bus stand road] for the past one and a half years, two years now. Work is at halt and a lot of dust is happening”.

Changes in Neighbourhood/Architecture

In Hubli, everyday activities once formed the essence of engagement and belonging. However, with rapid development and urbanisation, this dynamic has changed, altering the way people interact with their people and surroundings.

Places of belonging are spaces where individuals feel emotionally connected, accepted, and culturally rooted. For many, such spaces were found both around their homes and within the city—familiar streets, open grounds, and community gathering spots.

However, as the city has grown, many of these public spaces have either disappeared, lost their significance, or become exclusive. People now feel a growing disconnect—not only from the places they once felt belonged to but also from the newly built infrastructure, which fails to evoke the same sense of familiarity and attachment.

As a result, many interviewees expressed sorrow in changing scapes and loss of their open grounds. For Sanket, their childhood places in Renuka Nagar held a deep connection. The below image demonstrates the small life of Sanket's childhood that revolved around a small neighbourhood radius. Half of which doesn't exist and is currently gated under airport compounds.

As a child they spent most of their time around the locality and the ground behind their school, as shown in the figure below. They played with kites, cycles, in the open ground. They recall building tree houses every summer at their friends house which was close to their school. Currently they narrated how their open ground, school, houses around the school ground no longer exists. The drastic loss and changing scape of their area was due to land re-occupation by the airport authority. Their fabric of childhood places were built on the lands of airport authority, which allowed residential construction at the time. However, as the city grew, they chose to build the airport of Hubli.

VOICES OF CONCERN

What was then a concept of open park in the city, now it's just area parks. Every ward/area in Hubli has dedicated land for parks. Responsibility of these parks either fall directly under the HDMC or under the hands of area residents. But do these parks provide the space for leisure play? The answer was no to Sainath when I asked them about the state of parks. Sainath, notes in parks "Park, you get a restriction. You can't play cricket. You can't play something that is more activity based. You can't spoil the lawn. You only have to walk on the walking track. You can't sit wherever you want. I mean, what are you calling?". Many highlight similar concerns and note the kids have no space to play cricket, football and other games which require one to occupy the entire park. Hence there is rise in pvt sports grounds in Hubli like Playisto, Shri Durga Sports Academy, Sports Parc.

Parks not only lack space for kids to play but also fail to provide a recreational space for the youth. The primary reason being poor architecture that disallows community engagement or social interaction of youth in the parks.

Figure 5: Open ground behind school is now under the compounds of airport
Source: Author

As a result, Suhasni states that parks in the city seem less appealing to the younger generation. "While the spaces[parks] need to be open and non judgemental, there is also a need to create spaces that invites community engagement and activities". If parks don't allow space and social interaction of youth, how will there be a space for community engagement?

When I ask another respondent about the newly built tolan keri, a ticketed public park, she expresses that she doesn't like going there everyday. She doesn't resonate with the space. She tries explaining a need for a space similar to cubbon park "[People at cubbon park] they're just doing something fun or you just see people reading or painting or they're just doing something fun".

Here you don't do that. In fact, you try to do that. People will look at you like you're a weirdo. In fact, you'll feel quite uncomfortable doing that". Disconnection with space has heightened the problem of disconnect with people. Many people, especially youth living in the city across different areas have highlighted the lack of community engagement, interaction. Many youth have complained- "there is nothing to do in the city"[Sanket], nothing "activity based" [Sainath].

“In Hubli you need friends to kill time. There's no activity based things there's nothing that you can do alone over here”. Was this always the case? Sanket recalls: “See we are 2000 borns, when we were 13 where would our parents take us? Picnics, Market, Unkal kare nothing much. But today those spaces are also not accessible, Unkal kare is paid no one goes to picnic”.

Another respondent says “In Hubli you need friends to kill time. There's no activity based things there's nothing that you can do alone over here”. Was this always the case? Sanket recalls: “See we are 2000 borns, when we were 13 where would our parents take us? Picnics, Market, Unkal kare nothing much. But today those spaces are also not accessible, Unkal kare is paid no one goes to picnic”. As a result of all this, today one can observe that lack of space in public parks has forced youth to interact in parking lots or more often in cafes to spend their leisure time. The absence of such spaces has significantly impacted social interactions, creating a sense of disconnect among residents.

It's not just parks, but also changes in city architecture, from old vernacular buildings to tall apartments on the rise that's causing disconnect among citizens. The architecture of vernacular buildings created a space called "katti", which Sanket recalls. Katti is a space in front of a house that allows space to sit and interact with other people. Today there are no longer any katti's, remainants can be seen in the older part of the city. "That space [katti] is not there only in the apartment. Now imagine, you see if you are in the apartment you don't know who lives next door. Because there is no space to sit and talk." Community spaces are very crucial; change in architecture has resulted in changing social interactions and relationships with people around them in the city and diminishing opportunities for spontaneous conversations and community bonding.

Figure 6: Katti
Source: Author

Figure 7: Mitra Vishal Park, Area Garden
Source: Author

Dreams for Tomorrow

When asked about their future needs in the city, almost everyone compared Hubli to Bangalore. But many believed that Hubli is headed in a rapid pace of development that has changed the face of the city, it has attracted more business and subsequently more people migrating from different states. While from afar it seems like we are headed in a similar direction of Bangalore's development but we are far from reaching there.

To belong in a small city, participants in the past have experienced connection with nature and travel to the end of the city in less than 30 mins. These things have changed drastically since the introduction of smart city projects. This has impacted citizens' lives and changed their day to day experiences.

Roads were the major concern highlighted by all the participants. Many express frustration on the incompleteness of the project, poor execution, lack of planning, as a result of which citizens experience day to day problems on traffic, dust, safety concerns and parking problems. Citizens' vision for the coming years in this city is as basic as it could be, to solve the existing problems in the city. To have those perfect roads without dust, better traffic management and parking areas. For instance, Rishi suggests "Finish the construction as soon as possible, 90% problem will be solved", On the other hand the Sainath brings out an architectural problem that needs to be tackled in order to avoid traffic congestion, project failure, that is authorised bodies need to "introduce new infrastructure projects with thorough economic, social feasibility of the projects while also considering the physiological needs of the people". Sainath says that instead of constructing new spaces, the urban planners could consider demolishing the dead buildings and develop them. On the note for parking spaces, Jyoti reflects the need for "dedicated parking spaces in the Durgad bail market", another respondent also marks a similar point, "When outsiders start coming to the city, hubli should provide them with facilities - like major roads, parking systems, people following traffic rules".

Revitalized Green Spaces

Figure 8
Source: Author

With the introduction of urban planning and development projects, youth of the city warn everyone to avoid the problem that Bangalore created. They emphasise on the need to attract high ranking higher educational institutions, especially for MBA. Parallel they emphasize the need for diverse bachelors universities apart from engineering and medicine. There is a need for journalism, arts, social science, economics, philosophy, hospitality and tourism.

Youth also demand for more job opportunities so that they can retain themselves in their home town instead of migrating to bigger cities for better career options. In order to get the jobs, there is a need for bigger companies to establish themselves in the city. Currently the state and regional investment goes into supporting agriculture and MSME's cluster in the city.

It is not just the jobs but also providing us with the social infrastructure, as simple as redeveloping and maintaining the already existing parks which caters to everyone and creates a space to build trust and love amongst each other, welcome to everyone in the city Sanjay says - "Once you have love and care in the city everything else will fall in place. Then people also come together, clean up things"

Conclusion

Hubli stands at a crossroads of becoming the next big developed city in Karnataka. The city has witnessed rapid changes over a decade starting from 2013. This evolution has subsequently disrupted and impacted the everyday lives of people. Hubli has long been associated with the sense of home town, which holds the image of life which is slow, laid back and peaceful. With changing routines, there is an impact on the emotional level, when you see your place of belonging destroyed. The places where people felt most belonged to, are now the places they no longer visit or these are the places which don't exist.

“Once you have love and care in the city everything else will fall in place. Then people also come together, clean up things”

With changing routines, impact on the emotional level, there are evident concerns raised. Residents highlight a shift towards Hubli becoming a more dusty, noisy and traffic heavy space. The persistent problem of dust pollution which is the result of poor roads, digging, and stalled projects. The infrastructure projects and lack of free accessible public parks are also changing the way people interact with each other. Moreover, it is forcing youth to choose cafes over public spaces. As residents navigate these shifting scapes their stories reveal a need to revive the public spaces.

This document offers decision-makers an opportunity to recognize the crucial role of urban planning in maintaining community interactions. Effective urban planning should create spaces that uphold Hubli's cultural heritage while nurturing social connections, enabling citizens to thrive both as individuals and as a community.

Figure 9: Don't stamp on the grass
Source: Author

Figure 10: Walking time - 6:00 -9:00; 5:00-7:00
Source: Author

Fellowship was partly supported by :

Shreya Kabadi

Shreya is from Hubli and is currently working as an ESG Analyst while pursuing a passion for documentary photography. As a photographer, Shreya creates visual stories that highlight underrepresented narratives. In the future, Shreya wants to be involved in research and documentation across diverse areas—urban development, climate change, gender, and the queer community. She aspires to bring these stories to life through photo exhibits, documentary films, that foster dialogue and inclusivity, shedding light on critical issues and connecting with audiences to drive change and deepen understanding of our shared world.

Nāgrika Fellowship Coordinators:

Ravjyot Kaur | Research Associate

Praisya David | Research Associate

Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

